

Supporting Information

Electrocatalytic enhancement of CO methanation at the metal-electrolyte interface studied by *in situ* X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

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SOEC cell preparation, sample mounting, equipment and XPS data analysis

In the first step, the Pt/GDC and Ni(Cu)/8-YSZ cermet powders were synthesized. For Pt/GDC-10 (volume ratio 52:48) a wet-impregnation approach was followed. A pre-sintered (12 h, 1123 K, 5% H₂ in He) GDC-10 nanopowder (Gd_{0.1}Ce_{0.9}O_{1.95}, Sigma Aldrich, 99.9 %) was suspended in water. An aqueous solution of H₂PtCl₆ (Sigma Aldrich, 99.9 % trace metals basis) was added dropwise to the stirred suspension. After evaporation of the water and drying at 393 K for 5 h, the hygroscopic, red-brownish crystals were mortared and transferred into an alumina boat. The chloride-containing powder was decomposed by heating from 423 K to 573 K within 2 h in He atmosphere under the evolution of Cl₂ gas. After an oxidative (He:O₂ 1:1, 873 K, 3 h) and reductive (He:H₂ 5:1, 673 K, 3 h) treatment, the final powder was obtained. For the Ni(Cu)/8-YSZ cermet powder (volume ratio 1:1), an aqueous solution of Ni-nitrate (Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Alfa Aesar, 99,9985 % (metal basis)) and Cu-nitrate (Cu(NO₃)₂·6H₂O, Merck, 99.5 %) was added dropwise to an aqueous suspension of pre-sintered (12 h, 1123 K, 5% H₂ in He) 8-YSZ nanopowder (ZrO₂)_{0.92}(Y₂O₃)_{0.08} Sigma Aldrich, 99,9 % trace metals basis). An excess of NaOH solution (1 M) was slowly added to the stirred suspension. The precipitate was filtered, washed and dried (393 K, 72 h). The mortared powder was treated in He at 623 K for 3 h to decompose the metal hydroxides. An oxidative (He:O₂ 1:1, 1123 K, 3 h) and reductive (He:H₂ 5:1, 1073 K, 2 h) treatment was carried out to yield the final powder.

The cells were terminated with the respective Ni/8 YSZ or Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8 YSZ cathode layer on one side and with an anode layer made from Pt and GDC-10 on the other. The contacting wires and the powders were filled and smoothed out layer by layer into a pressing-body (diameter 10 mm) according to the following layered structure: Ni-wire // Ni(Cu)/8-YSZ // 8-YSZ // K-Type thermocouple // 8-YSZ // Pt/GDC // porous Pt // Pt-wire (Figure S6, B). The stack was pressed with 50 kN/cm² and sintered in a He:H₂ (5:1) mixture at 1523 K for 3 h. The final cell was then mounted on the sample holder and connected electrically (Figure S6, C). A scheme of the sample holder and the surrounding setup is shown in Figure S6, panel A. The embedded thermocouple inside the electrolyte layer allows for power control of an infrared heating laser (Figure S6,A). For the electrochemical experiments a BioLogic potentiostat was used. Product detection was achieved by on-line MS (Pfeiffer) directly attached to the NAP-XPS chamber. To investigate the electrochemically active zone within the Ni(Cu)/8-YSZ layer with a maximum of accessible TPD sites (i.e., the interfacial region between the working electrode and the electrolyte), a small concave pit was milled into the mounted cell (Figure S6, A). The

XPS data analysis was performed using the CasaXPS software, version 2.3.24 PR1.0 (Casa Software Ltd.). Fitting parameters were kept constant and originate from literature¹.

Figure S1. Panel A displays a scheme of the setup and the sample holder. In panel B, the layered structure of the cell is illustrated. Circular Ni and Pt wires with 125 µm thickness each were embedded in the respective electrode layers to ensure optimum electrical contact, and spot-welded 125 µm Ni and NiCr thermocouple wires were embedded in the 8-YSZ electrolyte layer. A photograph of the sample holder with mounted cell is shown in panel C.

XPS comparison of Ni/8-YSZ vs. Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8-YSZ upon carbon accumulation

Figure S1 confirms that carbon is accumulated via the TPB onto the porous cermet surface by presenting the qualitative visible decrease of the integral peak area of the Cu 2p, Ni 2p and Zr 3d region and the increase of the C 1s region. The top row shows the initial status before carbon growth (black traces), while the bottom row indicates the situation after electrochemically induced carbon growth in CO atmosphere. To prove if any oxidic state is present in the CuNi alloy, a spectrum of the Cu 2p and Ni 2p region recorded under H₂ atmosphere (0.5 mbar, brown trace, ensuring the metallic state of the alloy) was subtracted from the normalized experimental data (black trace). The residual (grey trace) shows no visible Cu(II) satellite feature in Cu 2p region and no oxidic species in the Ni 2p region confirming the purely metallic state of the alloy in CO atmosphere. The peak positions for a Ni₈₀Cu₂₀ alloy (Cu 2p_{3/2} = 932.6 eV and Ni 2p_{3/2} = 852.7 eV) are taken from ².

Figure S2. XP-spectra of the Cu2p, Ni2p, Zr3d and C1s region are exemplary shown for the Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8-YSZ electrode before (top row) and after (bottom row) electrochemically induced carbon growth recorded in CO atmosphere.

Thermodynamic promotion of CH₄ formation

Figure S2 supports the argumentation of an increase in CH₄ partial pressure and a decrease in Gibbs free energy for methane formation due to an increase of carbon activity, which can be achieved by cathodic electrochemical polarization.

Figure S3. The figure compares the thermodynamic results of reaction 6 for a given set of parameters ($p(\text{H}_2) = 0.375$ mbar and $T = 973$ K). The methane partial pressure (orange crosses) and the Gibbs free energy (blue circles) are plotted as a function of carbon activity.

QMS data analysis and Cyclovoltammetry I vs. E curves

From the experimental data we figured out that there is a clear dependence of applied potential and product detection via mass spectroscopy. We observe this dependence not only for the $m/z=15$ signal, but also for example for $m/z=44$ CO₂ (if CO is oxidized) or $m/z=18$ H₂O (if H₂ is oxidized; both not shown). Based on several experiments the delay time between the maximum applied potential during the CV and the QMS signal peak was found to be 90 s. The

delay-time corrected data are shown in Fig. 3 in the main paper. The I vs. E curves which corresponds to the data presented in Fig 3. (main paper) are shown in Figure S3.

Figure S4. Corresponding I vs. E curves to the data shown in Figure 3 in the main paper. A: Cathodic polarization of $\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Cu}_{20}/8\text{-YSZ}$ and B: cathodic and anodic polarization of $\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Cu}_{20}/8\text{-YSZ}$

Operando XPS comparison of Ni/8-YSZ vs. $\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Cu}_{20}/8\text{-YSZ}$ in CO/H_2 atmosphere

Figure S4 shows an operando experiment comparing Ni/8-YSZ vs. $\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Cu}_{20}/8\text{-YSZ}$ under chronoamperometric cathodic polarization of the WE in syngas atmosphere. While applying a bias of -1.00 V for Ni/8-YSZ and -1.25 V for $\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Cu}_{20}/8\text{-YSZ}$, the MS detects the additional methane product formation on-line and XPS validates the absence and presence of C_{TPB} for each type of electrode. The data support the statement in the main paper that the EPOC effect on Ni/8-YSZ vs. $\text{Ni}_{80}\text{Cu}_{20}/8\text{-YSZ}$ is proven qualitatively, but hard to distinguish quantitatively (panels B and D).

Figure S5. Operando XPS on Ni/8-YSZ (left side) vs. Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8-YSZ (right side). Panels A and C show the C 1s XP-spectra (green traces) recorded at 973 K in 0.500 mbar CO:H₂ = 1:3 atmosphere, while polarizations of -1.00 V (Ni/8-YSZ) and -1.25 V (Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8-YSZ) were applied to the WE. Panels B and D (light orange traces, raw and smoothed experimental data) show the electrochemically promoted excess methane formation caused by the chronoamperometric cathodic polarization.

To confirm the anticipated metallic state of Ni/Cu under the applied reductive conditions (CO:H₂ = 1:3) in Figure S5 we exemplarily show the Cu 2p and Ni 2p XP-spectra of the Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8-YSZ electrode. Figure S5 further compares a XP-spectra series recorded at OCP and at -1.25 V (same experiment as shown in Figure S4). In addition to the metals, the O 1s and C 1s XP-spectra for both potentials are shown. The C 1s data for E_{WE} = -1.25 V is the same as in Fig. S4, C. To prove if any oxidic state is present in the CuNi alloy, a spectrum of the Cu 2p and Ni 2p region recorded under H₂ atmosphere (0.5 mbar, brown trace, ensuring the metallic state of the alloy) was subtracted from the normalized experimental data (black trace). The residual (grey trace) shows no visible Cu(II) satellite feature in the Cu 2p region and no oxidic species in the Ni 2p region confirming the pure metallic state of the alloy in CO:H₂ atmosphere.

The weak feature in the oxidic Ni 2p region thus indicates a minor if at all oxidic contribution in the pure-metal spectrum recorded under H₂ (arrow). The peak positions for a Ni₈₀Cu₂₀ alloy (Cu 2p_{3/2} = 932.6 eV and Ni 2p_{3/2} = 852.7 eV) are taken from a XPS study of Kleiman et al. on NiCu alloys². The Ni/Cu ratio of 3.08 at OCP stays the same under polarization (3.07).

Figure S6. XP-spectra of the Cu2p, Ni2p, O1s and C1s region as well as an Auger spectrum of the CuLMM region are exemplary shown for the Ni₈₀Cu₂₀/8-YSZ electrode under OCP (bottom row) and under polarization ($E_{WE} = -1.25$ V, top row) recorded in CO:H₂=1:3 atmosphere.

To unravel the presence of a Cu(I) state on the electrode surface we fitted Auger spectra of the Cu LMM region recorded together with the experimental data shown in Figure S5 (same conditions). Figure S6 shown the Cu LMM Auger data and the results of the applied fitting routine according to Biesinger³. In the top and bottom spectra (i.e., under H₂ or CO:H₂ and OCP respectively) barely any Cu(I) state appears as a consequence of the fitting procedure. However, under an applied voltage of -1.25 V the contribution of Cu(I) increases. This observation may indicate some

electrochemically induced surface oxidic species, but due to the noisy spectrum and fast kinetics at 973 K this result is not reliable and could be an artefact. The KE of 918.3 eV for a Ni₈₀Cu₂₀ alloy was taken from literature².

Figure S7. Auger spectra of the Cu LMM region recorded under pure H₂ 0.5 mbar (top), under CO:H₂ 3:1 0.5 mbar and Ewe of -1.25 V (model) and under CO:H₂ 3:1 0.5 mbar and OCP (bottom). The fits and evaluation of the Cu(0) and Cu(I) state correspond to a routine published by Biesinger³.

References:

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